

Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints (early)

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Entry tags: (The) Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints, Christian Traditions, Latter Day Saints (Mormons), Religious Group

Latter-day Saints, more commonly known as "Mormons", are a sect of Christianity whose spiritual beliefs include an open scriptural canon, modern-day revelation, additional scripture, temple worship, divine priesthood authority, and a church structure that is a restoration of the Primitive Church of Jesus Christ.

Date Range: 1830 CE - 1951 CE

Region: Latter Day Saints (1830–1951)

Region tags: North America, United States of America

A map representing the early history of Mormonism.

Status of Participants:

✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

Sources

Print sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: The Book of Mormon
- Source 2: The Doctrine and Covenants
- Source 3: The Pearl of Great Price

Notes: While Latter-day Saints also use the King James Version of the Bible as an authoritative/canonical text, the preceding texts form the scriptural canon that is unique to Mormonism.

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Online sources for understanding this subject:

- Source 1 URL: <https://www.lds.org/?lang=eng>
- Source 1 Description: Official website for The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints
- Source 2 URL: <https://www.mormon.org/>
- Source 2 Description: Website that explores basic beliefs, doctrines, and principles of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

General Variables

Membership/Group Interactions

Are other religious groups in cultural contact with target religion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is the cultural contact competitive:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is the cultural contact accommodating/pluralistic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is the cultural contact neutral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is there violent conflict (within sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is there violent conflict (with groups outside the sample region):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does the religious group have a general process/system for assigning religious affiliation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Assigned at birth (membership is default for this society):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Assigned by personal choice:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Assigned by class:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Assigned at a specific age:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Assigned by gender:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Assigned by participation in a particular ritual:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Assigned by some other factor:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does the religious group actively proselytize and recruit new members:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Is proselytizing mandated for all adherents:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Is missionary work mandated for religious professionals:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Is missionary work mandated for all adherents:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Is proselytization coercive:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does the religion have official political support

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is there a conception of apostasy in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Are apostates prosecuted or punished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Apostates are socially shunned and/or publicly vilified:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Wealth, civil rights, and/or social capital are taken by authorities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Do apostates receive corporal punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Do apostates receive divine punishment:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Punished in the afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Cursed by "high god":

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Cursed by other supernatural being(s):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Other divine punishment:

– Yes [specify]: Removal of membership and revocation of priesthood, and temple, blessings

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Size and Structure

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (estimated population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Notes: There were 6 members at the founding of The Church of Jesus Christ of Latter-day Saints; by the year 1951, the total Church membership had risen to 1,147,157.

Number of adherents of religious group within sample region (% of sample region population, numerical):

– Field doesn't know

Nature of religious group [please select one]:

– Small religious group (actively discouraged-suppressed by larger religious group(s))

Scripture

Does the religious group have scriptures:

Scripture is a generic term used to designate revered texts that are considered particularly authoritative and sacred relative to other texts. Strictly speaking, it refers to written texts, but there are also “oral scriptures” (e.g. the Vedas of India).

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Are they written:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Are they oral:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Is there a story associated with the origin of scripture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Revealed by a high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Revealed by other supernatural being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Inspired by high god:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Inspired by other supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Originated from divine or semi-divine human beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Originated from non-divine human being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Architecture, Geography

Is monumental religious architecture present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ In the average settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Size of largest single religious monument, square meters:

– Square meters: 253015

Notes: These dimensions are for the Salt Lake City Temple; this temple is the most well-recognized Latter-day Saint structure to non-adherents.

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Height, meters: 68

Notes: These dimensions are for the Salt Lake City Temple; this temple is the most well-recognized Latter-day Saint structure to non-adherents.

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

- ↳ In the largest settlement, what percentage of area is taken up by all religious monuments:
 - Field doesn't know

Are there different types of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Tombs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Cemeteries:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Temples:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Altars:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Devotional markers:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Mass gathering point [plazas, courtyard, square. Places permanently demarcated using visible objects or structures]:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Other type of religious monumental architecture:

– Yes [specify]: Areas, and structures, important to early Church history are preserved

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is iconography present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Where is iconography present [select all that apply]:

– On persons

– At home

– Only religious public space

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Are there distinct features in the religious group's iconography:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Eyes (stylized or not):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Supernatural beings (zoomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Supernatural beings (geomorphic):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (anthropomorphic):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings (abstract symbol):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Portrayals of afterlife:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Aspects of doctrine (e.g. cross, trinity, Mithraic symbols):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Humans:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Other features of iconography:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Are there specific sites dedicated to sacred practice or considered sacred:

– Yes

↳ Are sacred site oriented to ecological features:

– No

Are pilgrimages present:

– No

Beliefs

Burial and Afterlife

Is a spirit-body distinction present:

Answer “no” only if personhood (or consciousness) is extinguished with death of the physical body. Answering yes does not necessarily imply the existence of Cartesian mind/body dualism, merely that some element of personhood (or consciousness) survives the death of the body.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as having qualitatively different powers or properties than other body parts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Spirit-mind is conceived of as non-material, ontologically distinct from body:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Other spirit-body relationship:

– Yes [specify]: The spirit and body, when combined, represent the soul of an individual

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Belief in afterlife:

– Yes

↳ Is the spatial location of the afterlife specified or described by the religious group:

– Yes

↳ Afterlife in specified realm of space beyond this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “above” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined “below” space:

– No

↳ Afterlife in vaguely defined horizontal space:

– No

↳ Afterlife located in "other" space:

– No

Reincarnation in this world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Are there special treatments for adherents' corpses:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Cremation:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Mummification:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ **Interment:**

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ **Corpse is flexed (legs are bent or body is crouched):**

– No

↳ **Corpse is extended (lying flat on front or back):**

– Yes

↳ **Corpse is upright (where body is interred in standing position):**

– No

↳ **Corpse is interred some other way:**

– No

↳ **Cannibalism:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ **Exposure to elements (e.g. air drying):**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ **Feeding to animals:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ **Secondary burial:**

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Re-treatment of corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Other intensive (in terms of time or resources expended) treatment of corpse :

– Yes [specify]: Adherents are buried in covenant clothing associated with temples

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Are formal burials present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

As cenotaphs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

In cemetery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Family tomb-crypt:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Domestic (individuals interred beneath house, or in areas used for normal domestic activities):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Other formal burial type:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Supernatural Beings

Are supernatural beings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ A supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god is anthropomorphic:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god is a sky deity:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god is chthonic (of the underworld):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god is fused with the monarch (king=high god):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god is a kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god has another type of loyalty-connection to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god is unquestionably good:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Other feature(s) of supreme high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god has knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme god's knowledge is restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted within the sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god's knowledge is unrestricted outside of sample region:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god knows your basic character (personal essence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god knows what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god has other knowledge of this world:

– Yes [specify]: Heavenly Father possesses all knowledge in the universe both spiritual and physical

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god has deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god can reward:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god can punish:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god has indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god exhibits positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god exhibits negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god possesses hunger:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Is it permissible to worship supernatural beings other than the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god possesses/exhibits some other feature:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ The supreme high god communicates with the living:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

In waking, everyday life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

In dreams:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

In trance possession:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Through divination practices:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Only through religious specialists:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Only through monarch

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Other form of communication with living:

– Yes [specify]: Through prayer, personal revelation, and priesthood blessings

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Previously human spirits are present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits can be seen:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits can be physically felt:

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Previously human spirits have knowledge of this world:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to particular domain of human affairs:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits' knowledge restricted to (a) specific area(s) within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted within the sample region:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits' knowledge unrestricted outside of sample region:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere normally visible (in public):
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits can see you everywhere (in the dark, at home):
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirit's can see inside heart/mind (hidden motives):
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits know your basic character (personal essence):
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits know what will happen to you, what you will do (future sight):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits have other form(s) of knowledge regarding this world:
– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits have deliberate causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits have indirect causal efficacy in the world:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits have memory of life:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits exhibit positive emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits exhibit negative emotion:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Human spirits communicate with the living:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Non-human supernatural beings are present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Does the religious group possess a pantheon of supernatural beings:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Supernatural Monitoring

Is supernatural monitoring present:

This refers to surveillance by supernatural beings of humans' behaviour and/or thought particularly as it relates to social norms or potential norm violations.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ There is supernatural monitoring of prosocial norm adherence in particular:

Prosocial norms are norms that enhance cooperation among members of the group, including obviously "moral" or "ethical" norms, but also extending to norms concerning honouring contracts and oaths, providing hospitality, coming to mutual aid in emergencies, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about taboos:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Food:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Sacred space(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Sacred object(s):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of coreligionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other religions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about murder of members of other polities:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about sex:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Adultery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Incest:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Other sexual practices:

– Yes [specify]: any sexual relationships or practices outside of the marriage between a man and a woman

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about lying:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about honouring oaths:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about laziness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about sorcery:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about non-lethal fighting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳

↳ Supernatural beings care about shirking risk:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about disrespecting elders:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about gossiping:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about property crimes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about proper ritual observance:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about performance of rituals:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about conversion of non-religionists:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about economic fairness:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about personal hygiene:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Supernatural beings care about other:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Do supernatural beings mete out punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Do supernatural beings bestow rewards:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Messianism/Eschatology

Are messianic beliefs present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Is the messiah's whereabouts or time of coming known?

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Is the messiah's purpose known:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Messiah is a political figure who restores political rule:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Messiah is a priestly figure who restores religious traditions:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Other purpose:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Norms and Moral Realism

Are general social norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is there a conventional vs. moral distinction in the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ What is the nature of this distinction:

– Present and clear

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Are specifically moral norms prescribed by the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are implicitly linked to vague metaphysical concepts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are explicitly linked to vague metaphysical entities:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked to impersonal cosmic order (e.g. karma):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked in some way to an anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are linked explicitly to commands of anthropomorphic being:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Specifically moral norms are have no special connection to metaphysical:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

- ↳ Moral norms apply to:
 - All individuals (any time period)
- Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Practices

Membership Costs and Practices

Does membership in this religious group require celibacy (full sexual abstinence):

– No

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require constraints on sexual activity (partial sexual abstinence):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

- ↳ Monogamy (males):
 - Yes
- Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

- ↳ Monogamy (females):
 - Yes
- Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

- ↳ Other sexual constraints (males):
 - Yes
- Specific to this answer:
Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

- ↳ Other sexual constraints (females):
 - Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require castration:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require fasting:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require forgone food opportunities (taboos on desired foods):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require permanent scarring or painful bodily alterations:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require painful physical positions or transitory painful wounds:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of adults:

"Adults" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition of a human who is 18-years-old or older and who is legally responsible for his/her actions, then please specify that difference in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of children:

"Children" here referring to an emic or indigenous category; if that category is different from the popular Western definition, please specify that different in the Comments/Sources: box below.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require self-sacrifice (suicide):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of property/valuable items:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

To other in-group members:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

To out-groups:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Destroyed:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require sacrifice of time (e.g., attendance at meetings or services, regular prayer, etc.):

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require physical risk taking:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require accepting ethical precepts:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require marginalization by out-group members:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require participation in small-scale rituals (private, household):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does membership in this religious group require participation in large-scale rituals:

i.e. involving two or more households; includes large-scale “ceremonies” and “festivals.”

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

On average, for large-scale rituals how many participants gather in one location:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

What is the average interval of time between performances (in hours):

Performances here refers to large-scale rituals.

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

Orthodoxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are interpreted in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper interpretation, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

Orthopraxy checks are mechanisms used to ensure that rituals are performed in a standardized way, e.g. through the supervisory prominence of a professionalized priesthood or other system of governance, appeal to texts detailing the proper procedure, etc.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Does participation entail synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Is there use of intoxicants:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Are extra-ritual in-group markers present:

E.g. special changes to appearance such as circumcision, tattoos, scarification, etc.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does the group employ fictive kinship terminology:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology universal:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology widespread:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Fictive kinship terminology employed but uncommon:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Society and Institutions

Levels of Social Complexity

The society to which the religious group belongs is best characterized as (please choose one):

– A state

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Welfare

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized famine relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is famine relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized poverty relief:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is poverty relief available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is institutionalized care for the elderly and infirm available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Education

Does the religious group provide formal education to its adherents:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is formal education available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Is extra-religious education open to both males and females:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Bureaucracy

Do the group's adherent's interact with a formal bureaucracy within their group:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with other institutional bureaucracies:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Public Works

Does the religious group in question provide public food storage:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is public food storage provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does the religious group in question provide water management (irrigation, flood control):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is water management provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does the religious group in question provide transportation infrastructure:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is transportation infrastructure provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Taxation

Does the religious group in question levy taxes or tithes:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Are taxes levied on the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Enforcement

Does the religious group in question provide an institutionalized police force:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized police force provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does the religious group in question provide institutionalized judges:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Do the group's adherents interact with an institutionalized judicial system provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does the religious group in question enforce institutionalized punishment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Are the group's adherents subject to institutionalized punishment enforced by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include execution:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Do the institutionalized punishments include exile:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

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↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include corporal punishments:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include ostracism:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

↳ Do the institutionalized punishments include seizure of property:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Does the religious group in question have a formal legal code:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Are the group's adherents subject to a formal legal code provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Warfare

Does religious group in question possess an institutionalized military:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Do the group's adherents participate in an institutionalized military provided by institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Are the group's adherents protected by or subject to an institutionalized military provided by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Written Language

Does the religious group in question possess its own distinct written language:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is a non-religion-specific written language available to the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is a non-religion-specific written language used by the group's adherents through an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Calendar

Does the religious group in question possess a formal calendar:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is a formal calendar provided for the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Food Production

Does the religious group in question provide food for themselves:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Is food provided to the group's adherents by an institution(s) other than the religious group in question:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE

Please characterize the forms/levels of food production [choose all that apply]:

– Large-scale agriculture (e.g., monocropping, organized irrigation systems)

Specific to this answer:

Date Range: 1820 CE - 2017 CE